

RECORDING THE ACTIVE SERVICE PROCESSES OF A SMALL-SCALE EVENT: APPLICATION ON A TRIATHLON SPORTING EVENT

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the current study is to define the contact-points of the visitors of a sport event with a view of recording the active service processes based on the undertaken duties and the requirements of every service. The application is made on AlmiraMAN, a triathlon sporting event, including swimming - biking - running, which took place in Katerini, Greece, on 2018. The emphasis is given on the athletes of the event (segment). Through the use of information record sheets, the findings reveal the identification of 12 contact-points and discuss the development of a Service Blueprinting System on a sporting event. Practical implications along with directions for future research are provided.

Key Words: Contact Points, Service Blueprinting, Sport Event, Triathlon.

INTRODUCTION

The number of participants (athletes) of small scale events typically surpasses the number of the audience (Gibson et al. 2012); consequently, athletes are the event's main customers (Vassiliadis & Fotiadis, 2016). However, small-scale event organizers face difficulties in attracting athletes because of the great number of similar events (Vassiliadis & Fotiadis, 2016). To that end, the attention to every detail of the organization procedure is recommended, seeing that situations such as disorganization or lack of signage may negatively affect event participation (Kaplanidou & Gibson, 2010). Organization (blueprinting) process may provide new prospects for small-scale event managers, enabling them to better understand the customers (athletes) needs and providing new paths for innovation (Gkarane & Vasiliadis, 2016; Gkarane & Vasiliadis, 2017).

Despite the growing interest in the study of small scale events, there is a scarcity as regards their planning process. This paper is set out to investigate the active service processes of a sporting event and to develop a blueprinting system with an aim to yield new understanding of the blueprinting procedure.

EXPLORATORY CASE STUDY OF ALMIRA MAN TRIATHLON SMALL SCALE SPORT EVENT

The methodology used in this paper is a blueprinting map, a method invented by Shostack (1982). It is based on the five parts that consist a typical service blueprint, according to Bitner et al. (2008); that is Customer Actions, Onstage/Visible Contact Employee Actions, Backstage/Invisible Contact Employee Actions, Support Processes, and Physical Evidence. The case study applied is AlmiraMAN race, a Triathlon small scale event, which takes place in the Olympic Coast of Katerini, Greece and includes open sea swimming, biking and running. It is organized every May since 2014 and lasts for two days. The product AlmiraMAN includes a mixture of athletic, instructive and entertainment services data.

Six students - volunteers undertake the role of the researcher for the contact points of the triathlon event AlmiraMAN May 2018 in order to note down and register the procedures. With the use of information record sheets, they define the real happenings of the event, time by time. The contact points are chosen based on the services that the event organizers provided (for instance, registration desk, parking etc). In our case, the emphasis is given to the triathlon athletes (segment) with a view of recording the providing of the active services based on the roles that have been taken over and on the requirements that are necessary at every contact point.

Table 1
Blueprinting Service Parts of AlmiraMAN 2018 Triathlon Event

Physical Evidence	AlmiraMAN website	Outdoor parking area	Secretary office & registration	Starting & Finishing Line	Swimming line & Sunbeds Area	Biking line	Running line	Beach Bar	Medical Area	Product Exhibition	WC, douche & bathroom area	Media, VIP & Ceremony Area
Customer Actions	Visit the website Register to participate	Arrive & park Take their cars and leave the area	Registration process, Take a competition number, b. chip and c. athlete's bag	Change clothes, Bike, finish Run, finish Return the chip Information where to have a shower and relax	Swim, Rest in the sunbeds after the end of the race, Drink coffee, Read books	Bike and finish	Run and finish	Make order at the stand, Relax, Eat, Drink, Socialize	First aid for lightly injured athletes	Visit the kiosks, Purchase athletic products	Use WC, take a shower, change clothes	Participate in awarding, photos and video with the rest athletes, organizers and VIP persons
<i>Contact Point Employee</i> Onstage Actions			Welcome, Check registration, Provide instructions and material Inform about the placement	Assistance to the athletes Provide clothing material Recording of athletes statements Distribute of fruit and energy drinks	Lifeguards check for potential problems during the swimming race Personnel serves drinks in the sunbed area	Updating for the athletes' position Distribute of water	Updating for the athletes' position Distribute bananas and water to the athletes	Preparation of the orders	Check for potential injuries	Welcome, Provide information and instructions regarding the use of the athletic products, Sell the products	Clean the area regularly	Congrats to all the athletes, award to the best ones Thanks to participant, sponsors, VIPs, volunteers. Take photos/videos
<i>Contact Point Employee</i> Backstage Actions			Prepare the bag for every athlete	Check the supply stations and the speaker system	Make drinks ready	Ready for possible tire inflation	Preparation of the fruit and water	Make drinks and food ready	Preparing the medical material Continuous contact with the National Emergency Center	Arrange bags for the products	Organize the access to the area Preparing the cleaning services Check for sanitary material and shortfalls	Invite and coordinate the VIPs, Organize the PR and media support, Bring the award material to the stage
Support Processes	Maintenance of the website Promotion of the race		Arrange all the back office support (tables, tents, notebooks, laptops) maintenance of the registration system	Coordination of the volunteer staff Preparation of the supply points	Prepare umbrellas and sunbeds, Arrange lifeboats Coordination of the volunteer staff	Prepare the road signals Coordination of the volunteer staff	Coordination of the volunteer staff Preparation of the supply points	Coordination and preparation of a. the drinks, b. the sandwiches, c. the beach bar space	Coordination of the medical staff, preparation of the wireless	Search and prepare the material suitable for athletes, Set up the kiosks	Maintenance of the area, Work on the signal material	Design and prepare the space and the stage construction Coordinate technicians, volunteers and personnel

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The study results in the identification of 12 Service Supply Demand Contact Points (Table 1) which delineate the athletes' activities at a practical level and will help to find out some gaps in the providing services of the race. Notwithstanding the fact that the event was successful, some weaknesses are spotted mainly as regards the parking area, the beach bar and the biking line. Specifically, although the parking space is ample, there is no personnel to assist the drivers and to provide them with instructions to park when arriving and departing. The result is that there are several vehicle obstructions and organizers make announcements during the event for vehicles removal. As a solution reservation seats for visitors and athletes should be adopted before the beginning of the event and some volunteers be in charge of parking support. Additionally, on the beach bar there are long queues since there is no waiter, except for one barman, and the customers can buy something only through self-service. Some volunteers could be responsible for this task so as to ensure that the athletes and visitors receive the service in an efficient manner. As concerns the biking line, it is noted that some bicyclists are chosen by stray dogs during the race. Thus, a better cooperation with the municipality is suggested along with the adoption of a communication channel among all the volunteers with an attempt to solve problems on the spot.

As a conclusion, before the delivery of a service, the customers' needs and requirements should be specified (Fließ & Kleinaltenkamp, 2004) and blueprinting systems be created to provide special experiences to the customers (Vassiliadis & Fotiadis, 2016). In AlmiraMAN case, our attention is turned to the amelioration of some of the providing services, with the main focus given on the volunteers and their role on the event. For example, a better traffic control regulation, larger number of volunteers with more visible vests in central points, no parked cars of the inhabitants at the race spots are suggested.

The findings can be used to identify the specific processes of an event structure that facilitate its preparation and provide a significant foundation for researchers in delving deeper into the event development through the application of more advanced blueprinting approaches. In terms of event management, this study provides an opportunity for the main stakeholders to improve their event planning agenda and opens a window through which the organizers involved can take new blueprinting aspects into consideration.

Limitations pertain to the fact that this research is conducted in Greece for a triathlon, a sporting event with unique characteristics. Further similar research is needed in international level for cross-country comparisons among several types of small scale events. Thus, researchers are encouraged to engage in empirical exploration of small-scale events as part of the planning strategy.

REFERENCES

- AlmiraMAN 2018, Triathlon, Retrieved from <https://www.AlmiraMAN.gr/AlmiraMAN.html>./ Accessed on February 28, 2019
- Bitner, M. J., Ostrom, A. L., & Morgan, F. N. (2008). Service blueprinting: a practical technique for service innovation. *California management review*, 50(3), 66-94. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41166446>
- Fließ, S., & Kleinaltenkamp, M. (2004). Blueprinting the service company: Managing service processes efficiently. *Journal of Business research*, 57(4), 392-404. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(02\)00273-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(02)00273-4)
- Gibson, H. J., Kaplanidou, K., & Kang, S. J. (2012). Small-scale event sport tourism: A case study in sustainable tourism. *Sport management review*, 15(2), 160-170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smr.2011.08.013>
- Sofia, G., & Chris, V. (2016). Blueprinting an event and tourist service marketing strategy: the case of the SMF Greek tourism small-scale sport event. In *Strategic Innovative Marketing: 4th IC-SIM, Mykonos, Greece 2015* (pp. 19-24). Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-33865-1_3
- Gkarane, S., & Vassiliadis, C. A. (2016). Blueprinting an event & customer oriented marketing mix: the case of the Sfindami Mountain Festival small scale event. *International Journal of Strategic Innovative Marketing*. DOI: 10.15556/IJSIM.03.01.002
- Kaplanidou, K., & Gibson, H. J. (2010). Predicting behavioral intentions of active event sport tourists: The case of a small-scale recurring sports event. *Journal of Sport & Tourism*, 15(2), 163-179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14775085.2010.498261>
- Shostack, G.L. (1982). How to design a service. *European Journal of Marketing*, 16(1), 49-63. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM000000004799>
- Vassiliadis, C. A., & Fotiadis, A. (2016). Managing Sport Tourism Experiences: Blueprinting Service Encounters. In *The Handbook of Managing and Marketing Tourism Experiences* (pp. 195-215). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78635-290-320161008>